

Age and gender estimation from speech to support the detection of Child Sexual Abuse Material

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A recent trend in speech processing is embedding generation models, which can encode much of the relevant information of an audio file in small vectors. This allows reusing these pre-trained models in other audio processing tasks without the need to train a complete model from scratch. A model for estimating a person's age can be used in different situations related to combating cybercrime. In such situations, LEAs may be interested in determining whether a voice in an audio or video comes from a minor to determine if the analyzed material could be related to Child Sexual Exploitation, for example.

This work compares five state-of-the-art models for generating fixed-size embedding vectors from speech for age and gender estimation using transfer learning.

We experiment on two well-known datasets, TIMIT and NISP, and five models: HuBERT and WavLM (each with two variations: base, large) and the single version of the XLSR-Wav2Vec2 model. The selected models were pre-trained for speech recognition with large datasets, including LibriSpeech, LibriLight, GigaSpeech, VoxPopuli, CommonVoice, BABEL, and Multilingual LibriSpeech. The models are composed of two blocks of neural layers, one is for generating an embedding for each 25 ms audio segment, and another block is for prediction.

This work inherits the advantages of fine-tuning deep neural networks on small datasets. It takes the acoustic capability of data modeling acquired by the models and reuses it in gender and age estimation tasks with smaller datasets. For this purpose, the weights of the encoder were frozen, and we added over them LSTM, Soft Attention, and a fully connected layer with two outputs, one for gender and another for age estimation.

In TIMIT, XLSR-Wav2Vec2 and HuBERT-base models achieve an accuracy of 0.992 for gender estimation, and WavLM-large achieves a mean average error (MAE) of 5.481 years for age estimation. In contrast, the WavLM-large model performed best in both tasks in NISP, with a 0.981 accuracy in gender estimation and an MAE of 3.593 years for age estimation.

The selected models for gender and age estimation tasks might be suitable for future research or real-world applications for user profiling, e.g., fighting against child sexual exploitation.